

Work Life Balance and Job Satisfaction - An Empirical Analyses Using Structural Equation Modeling

Dr .D. Shoba, Dr. G. Suganthi

Assistant Professor, PG Department of Business Administration, Guru Nanak College (Autonomous), Chennai.

Assistant Professor and Head, Department of Business Administration, ThiruKolanjiyappar Arts College, Vridhachalam.

Abstract

Work-Life balance has its importance from ancient days and the concept is very old, from the day the world has been created. There was a drastic change that has occurred in the market of teachers and their personal profiles. There are tremendous changes in different types of families which have bartered from the 'breadwinner' role of traditional men to single parent families and dual earning couples. This study provides an insight into work life balance and job satisfaction of School teachers working in Villupuram District. The sample comprises of 75 school teachers from Government and private schools in Villupuram District. The Study results that there is increasing mediating evidence in Work-life balance as well as Job satisfaction of teachers are not affected by the type of school in which they are working. The Work life balance of an individual is one of the factors which affect their satisfaction or happiness with life as a whole which can be measured through the construct of subjective well being.

1 INTRODUCTION

An Educational Institution is made up of people and its function through people. Without people, an Institution cannot exist. Teachers have two life spheres, i.e. personal sphere and work sphere. Personal spheres consist of marriage, family, kinship, neighbourhood, community, and Friendship. The work sphere means the action involving psychological or physiological efforts, executed in order to achieve an expected outcome. Teachers have to balance these spheres for better productivity. But, when we analyse ourselves, we identify that the balance is lost somewhere between work and life.

2 REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Basavaraj and Arun (2016) studied work life balance among university employees. Descriptive and Explorative research methodology where in the efforts are made to focus on the factors affecting work life balance among the university employees and the information needed for the same is collected through Secondary Data. The study reveals that whether employees are happy with their work life balance or not. In Result, the study identified the present employees/ work forces are not happy with their working style and environment. The current working circumstances are highly influenced by the adverse impact of globalization and high technological intervention. hence, it becomes challenge to the employer or higher authority to attract and retain the qualified employees by proving all necessary facilities, which are help full to maintain the work life balance and become more productive and efficient. Factor affecting work life balance of employees can be understood from the two different perspectives. They are from the perspective of employer standard working hours, organizational culture and practices, In house medical assistance, Leave Policy, Relationships between Peers, Flexible Working Hours and from the perspective (Marital Status, Number of Dependents (Children and Elder), Skills and Abilities to manage relationship).

Neha and Prashant (2016) studied the work life balance of working women in education sector in Indore city of Madhya Pradesh. The sample size for the present study was 150 which were collected from private education institutes. The software SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) 16.0 version and Microsoft Office Excel Worksheet 2007 were used. Factor analysis, KMO (kaiser- meyer- olkin measure of sampling adequacy) and Barlett test (chi-square, Df, sig) are the tools used for the study. The result indicated that due to changing scenario, the educational sector also demands the involvement of employees; therefore women have to give now more time and have to perform many responsibilities as compared to earlier time. So that women have to face almost same work life as women of corporate sectors face and it causes many adjustments in the life of women which should be understood by education managements and the families of working women.

3 WORK LIFE BALANCE AND JOB SATISFACTION

Work-life balance is a broad phenomenon which is complex and lacking in a global definition. Greenhaus (2001) and colleagues define work-family balance as the “extent to which an individual is equally engaged in -and equally satisfied with- his or her work role and family role”. Job satisfaction is the sense of a teacher which he obtains by doing the job that fulfils all his expectations. While morale refers to the group concept that is an attitude of all the teachers towards institution, job satisfaction is also one of the attitudes of an individual teacher. Job satisfaction has been defined as a ‘saturated, happiest or positive emotional state which is an outcome of the appraisal of one’s job or job experiences.

4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To analyse the Demographic, Individual and Organisational factors influencing work life balance.
2. To Study the relationship between work life balance and outcome Job satisfaction through Structural Equation Modelling.

5 RESEARCH DESIGN

The study is descriptive in nature whereby an attempt is made to highlight the work life balance and Job Satisfaction of a School Teachers working in Villupuram District.

5.1 Sample

A Disproportionate Stratified Random Sampling Method was done to select a sample of 75 school teachers from the teachers’ population in Villupuram district.

6 DATA ANALYSIS: STRUCTURAL MODELING

The conceptual model of this work studies and the relationships can be analyzed through Structural Equation Modeling wherein the relationship among independent variables is also tested to verify as to whether the different attributes taken for study are influencing job satisfaction of teachers through their work-life balance with interrelationships among them.

FIGURE 1

CHI-SQ = 18.975; DF = 12; P = .089;
 GFI = .992; AGFI = .970; CFI = .995; TLI = .986; RMSEA = .033

EI_Mean – Emotional Intelligence; Atti_mean – Atitude; Stres_mean– Stress Management; Flex_mean – Flexible working arrangement; Commit_mean – Organizational Commitment; WLC_mean – Work-life conflict; WLB_mean – Work-life balance; JOB_mean – Job satisfaction
 The results of the above conceptual model shows the Chi-square value of 18.975, with p =.089, GFI = 0.992; AGFI = 0.970; CFI = 0.995, TLI = 0.986 and RMSEA = 0.033. The values of the goodness of fit indexes suggest the norms of a reasonably high-fitting model are fully satisfied.

The regression weights of the parameters used in the model are appended in the following table 4.62 along with its significance in the model.

Table 1

Regression weights of parameters in Structural Model

Parameters	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
WLB_mean n	<-- -	Atti_mean	-0.418	0.051	-8.209	.000*
WLB_mean n	<-- -	Flex_mean	0.300	0.042	7.081	.000*
WLB_mean n	<-- -	WLC_mean	0.252	0.034	7.404	.000*
WLB_mean n	<-- -	Type	-0.001	0.023	-0.031	0.976
JOB_Mean n	<-- -	EI_Mean	0.294	0.039	7.63	.000*
JOB_Mean n	<-- -	Atti_mean	0.367	0.063	5.861	.000*
JOB_Mean n	<-- -	Commit_mean	0.445	0.039	11.36	.000*

JOB_Mean	<--	Type	-0.006	0.024	-0.261	0.794
JOB_Mean	<--	WLB_mean	-0.185	0.041	-4.509	.000*

* Significant at 1% level of significance

It can be noted from the above model that the relationship between Work-life balance and the attributes Attitude, Flexible working arrangement, Work-life conflict are significant at ($p < .001$) 1 per cent level of significance.

Table 2
Standardized effects of contributing factors

Standardized Total Effects						
	Organizational Commitment	Emotional Intelligence	Work-life conflict	Flexible working arrangement	Attitude	Work-life balance
Work-life balance	.000	.000	.332	.282	-.364	.000
Job satisfaction	.388	.285	-.043	-.036	.271	-.130
Standardized Direct Effects						
Work-life balance	.000	.000	.332	.282	-.364	.000
Job satisfaction	.388	.285	.000	.000	.224	-.130
Standardized Indirect Effects						
Work-life balance	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
Job satisfaction	.000	.000	-.043	-.036	.047	.000

The various hypotheses set in the model are tested for their validity and the result is reproduced in the following table:

Table3
Hypothesis testing of factors in the model

Hypothesis			R ²	P	Inference
Work-life balance	Attitude	Attitude does not have any impact on work-life balance	.215	.000*	Rejected
	Flexible	Flexible working		.000	Rejected

	e workin g arrange ment	arrangement does not have any impact on work-life balance		*	d
	Work- life conflic t	Work-life conflict does not have any impact on work-life balance		.000 *	Rejecte d
	Type of school	Job satisfaction of teachers does not vary among teachers working in Government, Aided and Private schools		.976	Not rejecte d
Job satisfa ction	Organi zationa l commi tment	Organizational commitment does not have any impact on Job satisfaction	.58 9	.000 *	Rejecte d
	Emotio nal intellig ence	Emotional intelligence does not have any impact on Job satisfaction		.000 *	Rejecte d
	Attitud e	Attitude does not have any impact on Job satisfaction		.000 *	Rejecte d
	Work life balanc e	Work-life balance does not have any impact on Job satisfaction		.794	Rejecte d
	Type of school	Job satisfaction of teachers does not vary among teachers working in Government, Aided and Private schools		.000 *	Rejecte d

* Significant at 1% level of significance

It can be seen from the above table that the low p-value ($< .01$) for the pairs of factors verify that the null hypotheses of no relationship between each pair of factors is strongly rejected at 1 per cent level of significance and it is concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between each pair of factors in the above table.

7 FINDINGS OF STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING

The work-life balance of teachers is significantly affected by the factors Attitude, Flexible working

arrangement and Work-life conflict. About 22 per cent of variation in the work-life balance of teachers is explained by the factors Attitude, Flexible working arrangement and Work-life conflict. The job satisfaction of teachers was significantly affected by the factors Organizational commitment, Emotional intelligence and Attitude of teachers.

Around 59 per cent of variation of job satisfaction is explained by the factors Organizational commitment, Emotional intelligence and Attitude of teachers. There is a low negative relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction of teachers, about 59 per cent of variation in job satisfaction is explained by indirect effect of factors through work-life balance; the factors Emotional intelligence, Organizational Commitment and Attitude of teachers are directly affecting job satisfaction, whereas the factors Flexible working hours and Work-life conflict have indirect effect on job satisfaction through work-life balance of teachers.

The attitude of teachers has a negative relationship with their work-life balance and Flexible working arrangement / Work-life conflict have a positive relationship with work-life balance. This implies that if the teachers have a positive or favourable attitude towards their work, they may spend more time and involved in their work, which may at times affect their family life. If the teachers are permitted to work in flexible hours, it will allow them to spend enough time with their required and especially at the time required by their family. The attributes Attitude of teachers, Emotional intelligence, and Organizational commitment have a significant positive relationship with their job satisfaction. This implies that if the teachers have a positive or favourable attitude towards their work, they will be satisfied on their job even though their work-life balance is slightly affected; also more the emotional intelligence of teachers, more is their job satisfaction; furthermore, if the teachers are committed towards the organization in which they may spend more time and involved in their work, which may at times affect their family life. Also if the teachers are permitted to work in flexible hours, it will allow them to spend enough time with their required and especially at the time required by their family. Neither work-life balance nor job satisfaction of teachers is affected by the type of school in which they are working. The levels of satisfaction of teachers on their work-life balance as well as on their job do not vary much with respect to the school in which they are working. The attributes Work-life Conflict, Flexible work arrangement and Attitude have direct effect on Work-life balance of teachers; Work-life conflict and Flexible working arrangement have a positive effect while the Attitude has a negative effect on work-life balance.

The attributes Organizational Commitment, Emotional Intelligence, Attitude and Work-life balance have a direct effect on the job satisfaction of teachers. The attributes Organizational commitment, Emotional intelligence and Attitude have positive effect while the attribute Work-life balance has a negative effect on job satisfaction of teachers. The attributes Work-life conflict, Flexible working arrangement and Attitude of teachers have also indirectly affecting job satisfaction through their work-life balance. The factors Work-life balance as well as Job satisfaction of teachers are not affected by the type of school in which they are working, i.e., the work-life balance of teachers working in Government school, Aided school and Private schools are same; also the job satisfaction of teachers is same irrespective of the school in which teachers are working.

8 RECOMMENDATIONS

It is suggested that the teachers should develop a favourable attitude towards their work and must love their profession which will ultimately raise their level of work-life balance and derive sole-satisfaction from their work. Different approaches to work-life balance: Presently many schools have leave arrangements for emergency situations to provide. But there should be more approaches to balance work-life which the schools can include in their work-life balance policy. They are as follows:

a. **Flexi-time** – The basic challenge in Education sector is that the schools cannot adopt the complete flexi time working system. But this option has been recently adopted by some private institutions. This can very well be implemented in other institutions as well.

b. **Job-sharing** – instead of having one full time teacher, the same job can be shared by two people on a part-time basis. Such an arrangement will ensure to a certain extent, balance in work- life.

c. **Sponsoring family, friendly activities like picnics/outing etc.** – arranging the family picnic and outing trips once a year, will also enhance the friendly relations among the teachers which would certainly benefit the development of inter-personal relationships.

d. **Time management workshops** - Arranging work-shops on time management once in a year will also help these teachers to understand and prioritize different activities on and off the job.

e. **Arranging Stress** – Conducting management and Meditation work-shop frequently will help the over-stressed teachers to cope up with the present health related issues.

f. **Job-related training** - Frequent job oriented training programs will enable them the intricacies of the job and improve the teacher's skill in handling the work and students.

Behavioural modeling technique helps to improve interpersonal competence through that teacher can overcome stress and attitudinal problem. This is an effective tool to improve the relationships between senior-subordinate, because problems which arise out of parents- students- Teachers – Management relations are, common in Schools.

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